

Beyond Open Research: Developing a Proof-of-Concept to Embed Quality and Reliability

Motivations for public involvement

PUBLIC	IMPERIAL
What would be your motivations to be involved in (fundamental) research?	What would be your motivations to involve public partners in (fundamental) research?
Directly involve you in something that is important for your community	Sharing findings
Shared understanding of the research that is being developed	To get public trust
Curiosity brings people in	Encourage public members to participate in future research
Desire to contribute to something good	Learning to share your findings to a non-expert audience
Develop understanding to overcome fear in the community and being represented	Better understanding of lived experience – this helps guide the research questions asked
Hable to have fun in lac and creating	Ensure your research matters to patients
Personal connection	To do research ethically
Understanding why fundamental research is important	Understand how acceptable the things we do in research are to the public
Understanding how public money is used	Improving public perception of research
Informed consent	Access to samples as research progresses

Science vs. values	Publications
Communicating	Visibility
Contributing to something bigger for the benefit of humanity	Caring about specific community
Rewarding	Public recognition about the project
Not targeting the right area. More engagement should be done to find the targeted population	Bringing researchers' attention to the community that they study – Not much black people in the research project. Can create awareness to the lack of community. It's beneficial from the recruitment point of view (good for Equality, Diversity and Inclusivity)
Fun	Fun
Financial (initially)	Engage and empower people to engage with their health
Gaining more knowledge about research and how I can use research and outputs	Motivational – to keep researching when you see people's enthusiasm
The research benefits you personally	Justify our funding to taxpayers
Creative – more ideas to work on	Get new ideas from the public
Can ask questions to the specialists	
Sense of belonging	
Understanding my health, my family's health, risks and inheritance	
Reciprocity	
Helping other people / make a difference	
Applying genetic engineering to improve behavioural / cognitive issues	
What is biology? What is psychology?	

PUBLIC	IMPERIAL
What can be done to have meaningful public involvement in the project?	How does public involvement in this project affect research quality and/or reliability
Make information/data more accessible to public/non-expert audience	Incentives for researchers to make research transparent /accessible
Information need to be transparent	By involving public, you develop knowledge about their need and how to reach them
Engagement can be improved by providing activities in different formats, just no text	Need to understand your audience in order to target them with the right information
Meaningful involvement translates in people leaving with something to think of	Meaningful involvement from the public will encourage researchers to carry on involving public in future projects
Getting questions from public can be a good sign of meaningful involvement	Public meaningful involvement will shape somehow the researcher's approach to the project
Invite the public – How to do this effectively?	Teach researchers how they can better reach and engage the public
Visibility of what fundamental research is being done and why	Makes research more representative
Cochrane collaboration collects and disseminates systematic reviews which shows what is needed in terms of platforms → condenses good and bad evidence in an accessible way for doctors and public	Importance of lay language to explain research in a clearer way. Engaging newspapers editors as they're mostly bridge between

	public and researchers. This could increase research quality and public trust in research as they could understand research process
Consumer network for public which produces lay summaries	Funders integrate public and patient involvement
Increasing public trust is essential	Funders need to provide research money for engagement activities
Ensure ways of involving people by meeting individuals' accessibility needs so that they don't become barriers -it's involvement + engagement	Involving public can improve funding perspectives (but this shouldn't be a motivation as a 'tick box' exercise)
Being able to talk to researcher	Feedback
Seeing change / impact	Repeat engagement
Enriching methods to engage people for young/old people	Word of mouth – new participants
Make it interesting to the public	Simplified, condensed but transparent information
Raw ideas can be powerful if processed	Finding right research questions that matter to the public
Use ideas from ordinary public to open new avenues	Improves research quality and makes outputs more impactful
Make research attractive to ordinary public	PI's need to be the people engaging with the public – they are the one writing grants
	Stop getting bogged down in narrow pathways
	Outreach – diversity
	Better, more accessible literature